

Original Research Article

Volume 15 Issue 06

June 2026

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.21073580](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21073580)

A SUCCESSFUL AYURVEDA MANAGEMENT OF *VICHARCHIKA* (ECZEMA) WITH *SHAMANA CHIKITSA*: A CASE REPORT

Dr Kamayani Mishra

M.D. (Dravyaguna), Ayurveda Medical Officer,

Pandit Uddhav Das Mehta Government Ayurveda Hospital, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

Email: drkamayanimishra9@gmail.com

Abstract

Vicharchika is a *Kshudra Kushtha* described in Ayurveda, predominantly involving *Kapha-Pitta Dosha* with *Rakta* and *Twak Dushti*. It commonly presents with *Kandu* (itching), *Shyava Varna* (hyperpigmentation), *Rukshata* (dryness), *Twak Vaivarnya* (discoloration), and *Shotha* (swelling). This case study presents the successful management of a chronic case of Vicharchika affecting the lower limb using *Khadiradi Vati*, *Mahamanjishthadi Kwatha*, *Arogyavardhini Vati*, and local application of *Marichyadi Taila*.

Keywords: *Vicharchika*, *Eczema*, *Kushtha*.

Introduction

Vicharchika is characterized by intense itching, discoloration, dryness, scaling, and lichenification of the skin. It resembles chronic eczema or stasis dermatitis in contemporary medicine. *Ayurvedic* treatment focuses on *Dosha Shamana*, *Rakta Prasadana*, *Deepana-Pachana*, and *Twak Prasadana*.

Vicharchika is described under *Kshudra Kushtha* in *Ayurvedic* classics and is characterized by *Kandu* (itching), *Shyava Varna* (blackish discoloration), *Pidika* (eruptions), *Bahusrava* (profuse discharge), and *Raji* (lichenification-like skin markings). The disease predominantly involves vitiated *Kapha* and *Pitta Doshas* along with *Rakta Dushti*, resulting in chronic dermatological manifestations resembling eczema.^{1,2}

Case Presentation

Patient Information

Age: 55 years

Gender: Male

Occupation: Businessman

Chief Complaints:

- Hyperpigmentation of right foot and ankle
- Dryness and scaling
- Mild swelling of foot and ankle
- Itching for 2 years
- Cosmetic discomfort and
- difficulty in walking due to swelling

History of Present Illness

The patient presented with chronic discoloration and dryness over the dorsum of the foot and lower leg associated with intermittent itching and oedema. Symptoms had gradually increased over the last two years. Previous conventional treatment provided only temporary relief.

Examination

Before Treatment (Image 1)

Clinical findings:

- Marked hyperpigmentation over foot and ankle
- Diffuse oedema
- Dry, scaly skin
- Multiple hyper pigmented macules
- Thickened skin with lichenification
- Mild itching

Ashtavidha Pariksha

Nadi: Kapha-Pitta

Mala: Prakrita

Mutra: Prakrita

Jihva: Sama

Shabda: Prakrita

Sparsha: Ruksha

Drik: Prakrita

Aakruti: Madhyama

Dashavidha Pariksha

Prakriti: Kapha-Pitta

Vikriti: Kapha-Pitta Dushti

Sara: Madhyama

Samhanana: Madhyama

Satmya: Madhyama

Satva: Madhyama

Ahara Shakti: Madhyama

Vyayama Shakti: Madhyama

Vaya: Madhyama

Diagnosis

The patient was assessed according to the principles of *Ashtavidha Pariksha* (eightfold examination) and *Dashavidha Pariksha* (tenfold examination). The findings revealed *Kapha-Pitta* predominance with evidence of *Kapha-Pitta Dushti*. These examination methods are described as essential diagnostic tools in Ayurveda for determining the patient's constitution (*Prakriti*), disease status (*Vikriti*), strength, and prognosis.^{3,4}

Treatment Protocol

Internal Medicines		
Medicine	Dose	Duration
<i>Khadiradi Vati</i>	2 tablets twice daily	8 weeks
<i>Mahamanjishthadi Kwatha</i>	20 ml twice daily with an equal amount of water	8 weeks
<i>Arogyavardhini Vati</i>	<i>Arogyavardhini Vati</i>	8 weeks

External Application		
Medicine	Method	
<i>Marichyadi Taila</i>	Local application twice daily over affected area	

The patient was advised to follow a *Pathya Ahara-Vihara* regimen aimed at pacifying *Kapha* and *Pitta Doshas* and correcting *Rakta Dushti*. A light and easily digestible diet, increased consumption of green vegetables, and adequate hydration were recommended. The patient was instructed to avoid excessively spicy, oily, fermented, and incompatible foods, along with curd, bakery products, junk foods, and daytime sleep, as these are considered aggravating factors for *Kushtha* and other skin disorders.⁵⁻⁷

Results

After Treatment (Image 2)

Observed improvements:

- Significant reduction in oedema
- Decrease in hyperpigmentation
- Reduction in skin dryness and scaling
- Improvement in skin texture
- Relief in itching
- Better cosmetic appearance

Assessment	Parameter Before Treatment	Parameter After Treatment
Itching	Moderate	Mild
Swelling	Moderate	Nil
Hyperpigmentation	Severe	Mild
Dryness	Severe	Mild
Skin texture	Thickened	Near normal

Discussion

Mahamanjishthadi Kwatha acts as an effective *Rakta Shodhaka* and anti-inflammatory formulation, reducing *Rakta Dushti* and improving microcirculation. *Arogyavardhini Vati* enhances Agni, corrects metabolic disturbances, and supports liver function, thereby aiding detoxification. *Khadiradi Vati* possesses *Kushthaghna*, *Kandughna*, and *Rakta-Prasadana* properties, helping in chronic skin disorders. *Marichyadi Taila* provides local anti-inflammatory and *Kapha-Vata* pacifying action, reducing dryness, scaling, and discoloration. The combined effect of these formulations resulted in significant improvement in clinical symptoms and restoration of skin health.

Conclusion

This case demonstrates that *Ayurvedic* management using *Khadiradi Vati*, *Mahamanjishthadi Kwatha*, *Arogyavardhini Vati*, and *Marichyadi Taila* can effectively manage chronic *Vicharchika* associated with hyperpigmentation, oedema, dryness, and itching. Significant clinical improvement was observed without adverse effects, highlighting the potential of Ayurveda in chronic dermatological conditions.

References

1. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala. *Charaka Samhita*. Nidana Sthana. Kushtha Nidana Adhyaya. Ch. 5. In: Tripathi B, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan; 2020.
2. Vagbhata. *Ashtanga Hridaya*. Nidana Sthana. Kushtha Nidana Adhyaya. Ch. 14. In: Murthy KRS, translator. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy; 2018.
3. Vagbhata. *Ashtanga Hridaya*. Sutra Sthana. Ayushkamiya Adhyaya. Ch. 1. In: Murthy KRS, translator. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy; 2018.
4. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala. *Charaka Samhita*. Vimana Sthana. Rogabhishagjitiya Vimana. Ch. 8. In: Tripathi B, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan; 2020.
5. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala. *Charaka Samhita*. Chikitsa Sthana. Kushtha Chikitsa Adhyaya. Ch. 7. In: Tripathi B, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan; 2020.
6. Sushruta. *Sushruta Samhita*. Chikitsa Sthana. Kushtha Chikitsa Adhyaya. Ch. 9. In: Sharma PV, editor-translator. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Vishvabharati; 2019.
7. Vagbhata. *Ashtanga Hridaya*. Chikitsa Sthana. Kushtha Chikitsa Adhyaya. Ch. 19. In: Murthy KRS, translator. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy; 2018.